

STUDIES OF THE INFLUENCE OF CULVERTS ON THE UPPER STRUCTURE OF THE PATH

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Abstract: *In this article, the analysis of the culvert capacity of the pipe is carried out and, based on the data obtained, the effect on the state of the path is investigated.*

Keywords: *Pipes, rails, irregularities, measurements, indicator, filling of pipes experimental section.*

Introduction. The durability of rails, the comfort of high-speed and high-speed trains, and the wear of rolling stock are largely related to the condition of culverts. This article examines the relationship between the operational condition of culverts and the quality and safety of road traffic, also conducted for roads with the improvement of the upper structure of the track[1.3.4.6.8.10]. For a probabilistic assessment and analysis of the dependence of the transport and operational condition of the upper structure of the track on the operational condition of culverts, it is necessary to rank data on the types of defects depending on the factor that best describes this relationship. The determination of the relationship between the condition of the culvert and the quality of the upper structure of the path is carried out through the amount of filling of the embankment above the pipe, so this characteristic will also indirectly take into account the magnitude of the impact of the transport load on the structure and the stability (resistance) of the embankment to this effect.

On operated roads, the size of the embankment above the pipe consists of a combination of two elements: the thickness of the protective layer (embankment) above the pipe and the thickness of the layers of the pavement structure. Since it is not allowed to set the thickness of the embankment above the pipe on the operated road by direct method (drilling wells) due to the possibility of damage and destruction of the pipe body, the average thickness of the embankment above the pipe was determined geometrically, based on the results of leveling or total station survey. The systematization of culvert defects was carried out in two categories: culvert defects and coating defects caused by the condition of culverts. Defects of culverts: 1 – stagnation of water at the ends of the pipe; 2 – local destruction of the fortifications of the slopes; 3 – silting of the pipe; 4 – violation of the tightness of the joints; 5 – separation of the links; 6 – partial destruction of the heads. Defects on the coating caused by the condition of culverts: 7 – trackage; 8 – potholes; 9 – waves; 10 – subsidence; 11 – depths; 12 – opening of the pipe body[2.5.7.9].

The results of systematization are presented in the study of the presence of a culvert randomly within the Tashkent - Samarkand line, three experimental sites were assigned, the characteristics of which are given in Table 1.

№	Hole Type	Number of fixed defects												Number of pipes	Number of observations
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
1)	round	8	0	6	0	0	13	0	0	0	4	0	0	25	13
2)	rectangular	6	0	10	0	0	17	0	0	0	9	0	0	20	17
3)	round rectangular	10	0	5	0	0	9	0	0	0	7	0	0	16	10

Conclusions. The technical condition is the main characteristic of the ability of the pipes to provide a normal operating mode associated with the safe passage of trains with set speeds and uninterrupted passage of the watercourse through the body of the embankment. The main indicators of the technical condition are considered to be the actual bearing capacity of the pipe elements, as well as the degree of development of various violations of hydraulic and other functions of the structures. In real conditions, the current technical condition of artificial structures operated on railways is characterized by the presence of signs limiting the possibility of increasing the axial and linear loads of freight cars. This, in turn, is a deterrent to increasing the capacity of railway sections. In accordance, further scientific research is necessary to solve the problem of improving the operational reliability of culverts.

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